

A Strategic Investment Decision Model for Maximizing Financial Performance: With a Case of Dry Bulk Shipping Business

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Abstract: *This paper deals with a managerial decision to maximize net income for shipping business characterized by both high operational and financial risks. Particularly, dry bulk carrier shipping business has shown repeatedly dramatic market cycles since year 1980. This case analysis for dry bulk shipping business is attempted to verify the effectiveness of proposed investment decision model in terms of financial performance for a specific period where the freight market experienced another huge business cycle. Since the tramp shipping business is capital-intensive and high risk industry, managers are required to avoid these business risks and maximize business profit consisting of operational income and capital gain by asset play. In essence, the managers are required to make timely and rational decision in both sale and purchase of their ships. There are three alternatives in investment on shipping business: i.e. chartering, second-hand ship, and new shipbuilding. This case study assumes that a shipping company is able to choose the alternatives of chartering and purchasing second-hand ships in their investment decision because the new shipbuilding requires at least 2 years for delivery and operation.*

The financial results of case analyses under dynamic business environment and condition reveal that the managers must pay keen attention to secondhand ship market greatly depending on freight market showing recession, recovery, boom, and collapse. In sum shipping company has to buy a ship at the lowest price during the recession stage and sell it at the highest price during the boom stage and put a chartered ship into the service line for customers rather than keep operating the ship for the whole freight market cycle in which the company has no choice but to suffer a huge loss due to high operational and financial costs as well as to sharp decrease in revenues.

Key words: *Investment decision model, Operational and financial risks, Assetplay, Secondhand ship market, Freight market cycle,*

I. Introduction

Since the shipping industry contributed to promoting international trade and economic growth, many ambitious countries have made an intensive effort to invest on shipping business. There are two major business sectors in shipping industry. One is liner business and the other one is tramp business. Containership is a symbol of liner business and bulk carrier is that of non-liner business. The liner shipping market has shown a relatively controllable and predictable pattern in its business management, whereas the tramp shipping market has revealed a dramatic business cycle as depicted in <Fig. 1>. The dry bulk carrier business, which claims the largest portion of non-liner business sector, covers sea transportation of iron ore, coal, grain, and various dry raw materials for industrial uses. However, there have been a couple of catastrophic business results in tramp shipping business in Korea since 1980.

<Fig.1> Historical Baltic Dry Index and shipbuilding price for panamax Bulker

So it is necessary to figure out the reason why many bulk shipping firms suffered the enormous financial losses in term of timing on investment decision. In general, shipping industry is exposed to two business risks including financial risk and operational risk. Particularly the magnitude of operational risk is far greater than that of financial risk because the freight markets have experienced the unexpected rises and collapses in a short time while the interest rates have remained low for a long time. Beenstock(1985 and 1993) performed a pilot study in dealing with an investment decision model for shipping business in attempting to avoid both financial and operational risks. Vergottis(1993), Sjogren(1999), and Batchelor(2007) also made some contribution to making investment decision for improving net profit of shipping business with a focus on freight market prediction. Among them the decision model established by Beenstock was very impressive in maximizing business performance of tramp shipping business. The model is hypothesized to maximize a total business profit consisting of operating profit and capital gain obtainable by asset play which means buying ship at lowest price and selling at highest price appropriately.

In chapter II, the dry bulk shipping business risks will be analyze to justify that the strategic investment decision model is very effective in attempting to maximize the financial performance. We also deal with the analyses of costs associated with dry bulk shipping business. Chapter III includes the results of two case analyses on net cash inflow in terms of two different investment timings. In Chapter IV, some concluding remarks will be given on the basis of the analyses results.

II. Strategic Investment Decision Model Building under Freight Market Uncertainty

(1) Model Building

Every industry experiences a business cycle in the market. But normally many cases are not so severe and uncontrollable. However, shipping industry, especially non-linear shipping business like dry bulk sector, has shown a dramatic freight market change. In parallel with the freight market, the ship market has also fluctuated remarkably as shown in <Fig. 1>. The primary reason why many shipping firms have failed to achieve their financial goals is that they make investment decision to purchase or charter the vessels not in the recession period but in the boom time in which the ship price is very expensive. If the freight market turns from boom stage to collapse, the shipping companies are subject to huge financial losses owing to high costs as well as to intolerable decrease in freight revenue. As a result of the unique dry bulk shipping business cycle, ship-owners are required to pay keen attention to capital gain by timely asset-play of sale and purchase. In many cases, the capital gains are far greater than operational profits. Without considering asset-play and time-chartering, the dry bulk business is not able to cope with the volatile freight markets. The original investment decision model suggested by Beenstock(1985) is as follows:

$$R_t = \sum_{i=1}^t \{F_i - (FC_i + VC_i)\} / P + (E_{t+1} - P) / P \quad \text{---(1)}$$

where, R_t : accumulated ROI during t years

F_i : Freight Revenue in year t

VC_i : Variable cost(Operating cost) in year t

FC_i :Fixed cost(Ship cost) in year t

$E_{(P+1)}$: Ship price in year of sale
 P : Ship price in year of purchase

The model (1) represents an expected cumulative return on investment(ROI) during the investment period of t years. In order to maximize the R_i , the managers should be able to make decision on timing both for investment and paying off. Put it differently, timing for purchase of ship should be in a recession stage in which the ship price remains very low and timing for ship sale should be in boom stage where the ship price goes up to maximum level. This investment decision allows the shipping company to enjoy a considerable capital gain as well as cumulative operational income for t years. But many shipping companies have failed to follow this model. In many cases, they are very active to make investment decision during q boom stage at the highest ship price and forced to sell out their expensive assets at the lowest price during a recession period. As a result, they suffer a huge financial loss mainly because of failure in timing of ship's sale-and-purchase.

Using the model(1), the following applied model is formulated for cash flow analysis on two investment alternatives.

$$\text{Max NPV} = \sum (R_t - C_t)/(1+i)^t + CG_n/(1+i)^n \quad \text{---(2)}$$

Where, NPV : Cumulative Net Present Value for t years

R_t : Total Freight Revenue for t years

C_t : Total cost including Fixed and Variable costs for t years

i : Discount Rate

CG_n : Capital gain in Year n(Purchase price - Sale price)

Since the model (1) ignores the time value for multiple periods, the model(2) represents the concept of net present value(NPV) using a discount rate for a business duration.

(2) Revenue and Cost Analyses

In order to perform the case analyses associated with investment decision alternatives, it is necessary to estimate the shipping costs in both finance and operations. There are three cost categories in shipping business; i.e., ship cost, voyage cost, and capital cost. The ship cost includes manning, lubricant, supplies, administrative cost, insurance, maintenance and repairs. The voyage cost is classified into Port dues, fuel cost, agencies, and some other variable costs. The financial cost means interests paid including the debt payments. If the investors purchased the ship assets at peak time, they should pay more interests cost and have no chance to take a capital gain by asset play. So the most important investment decision is when to purchase ships. If they purchased the ship assets at the bottom of the ship market, they can save the financial cost and have an opportunity to enjoy a capital gain by favorable asset play.

Assuming that an investment decision be made for year 2006-2010, the revenue and cost of operating a 70,000-dwt secondhand ship, putting into the shipping route for carrying grain between West coast of USA and Japan can be estimated appropriately. Usually manning cost dominates other ship costs while fuel cost is a leading one among the operational costs. So the oil price is very sensitive to net income of shipping business.

Meanwhile, shipping industry is very vulnerable to both operational risk and financial risk because of its dramatic business cycle and heavy debt-financing. The equations of (3) and (4) stand for degree of operational leverage(DOL) and that of financial leverage(DFL).

$$\text{DOL} = \frac{Q(F-VC)}{\{Q(F-VC) - FC\}} \quad \text{----- (3)}$$

$$\text{DFL} = \frac{\text{EBDIT}}{(\text{EBDIT} - \text{DI})} \quad \text{----- (4)}$$

The equation (3) implies contribution margin "Q(F-VC)" divided by profit "Q(F-VC) - FC". If the value of DOL shows higher, the operational risk is also high. The equation (4) represents earnings before depreciation, interest, and tax(EBDIT) divided by "EBDIT" minus depreciation and interest paid. If the value of DFL is high, the financial risk is also high. Even the DOLs and DFLs of many shipping firms have shown negative values due to their huge cumulative operational loss. Under this business condition, the shipowners are required to make a profitable investment decision on the basis of asset play.

III. Evaluation of Investment Alternatives in Cash Flows and Timing

Using the decision model with relevant assumption, two investment alternatives are considered to verify the importance of timing for sale and purchase of ship. The first alternative is to purchase a ship in 2003 where the bulk shipping market was in recession stage and to sell out the ship in 2008 where the freight market was in boom stage as well as the ship price remained very high. The second alternative is to buy a ship in 2005 where the bulk shipping market was in recovery stage and to sell out the ship in 2010 where the market was in another recession stage. In order to compare the investment result of the first alternative with that of second one, the additional assumptions are made as below:

- 1) The investment period is 6 years. But the year in which each investment decision was made is different.
- 2) The 5-year old ship is a Panamax(70,000 dwt) type for carrying grain and running between West coast of North America and Far East Asia.
- 3) Considering the days at sea and in port, the annual no. of voyage is fixed 10.

Using these assumptions, the cash flow analyses on two investment alternatives can be performed as shown in <Table 1>. The freight revenue of both first and second investment decision can be figured out by multiplying dead-weight ton(70,000) and annual average freight rate per ton. Since the total cost consists of ship cost, voyage cost, capital cost, and depreciation cost, the summation of these costs will be the actual total cost for cash outflow. However depreciation cost is a cost without cash outflow.

The first investment choice, in which the manager purchased the panamax-typed bulk ship at \$13.5 million and sold it out at \$25.6 million, enjoyed a large capital gain of \$12.1 million by asset-play. But the second investment choice, in which the decision-maker purchased the same typed ship at \$17.2 million and sold it out at \$15.8 million, suffered a capital loss of \$1.4 million. The final total cash flows of two investment alternatives show \$68.4 million and \$14.8 million respectively. This implies the cash inflow of first investment choice largely surpassed that of second choice.

<Table 1> Cash Flow Anysis on two Investment Alternatives for Panamax-typed Grain Bulk Carrier									
Unit: million US\$									
Year	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	
Ship Price (Sale & Purchase)	13.5		17.2			25.6		15.8	
Freight Rev.	6	10.9	10.5	8.1	10.2	23.5	5.3	5.95	
dwt	70000								
freight/ton(US\$)	8.5	15.5	15	11.5	14.5	33.5	7.5	8.5	
no. of Voy.	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	
Expenses									
1) Ship Cost	1.9	2.8	2.7	2.3	2.5	3.8	3.1	3.5	
2) Voyage Cost	2.7	3.5	3.9	4.9	5.8	7.6	5.5	5.8	
3) Capital Cost(1)	0.34	0.31	0.31	0.34	0.27	0.27			
Capital Cost(2)			0.39	0.43	0.35	0.34	0.39	0.39	
4) Depreciation cost(1)	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.68			
Depreciation Cost(2)			0.86	0.86	0.86	0.86	0.86	0.86	
Cash from Operation(1)	4.2	9.6	8.8	4.6	6.6	22.5			
Cash From Operation(2)			4.5	1.4	2.5	12.7	-2.4	-2.5	
Capital gain from Sale &Purchase(1)						12.1			
Capital gain from Sale &Purchase(2)								-1.4	
Total Net Cashflow(1)						68.4			
Tota Net Cashflow(2)								14.8	

VI. Conclusions

Judging from the results of these cash flow analyses, the investment decision makers are required to consider investment timing issue, which is critical to achieving the higher financial performance, particularly in terms of dramatic change in ship price and freight market. To put it differently, it seems impossible for managers to improve their business performance without successful asset-play of “buy-low and sell-high”.

Considering the financial results of the previous chapter, under the given condition, the managers are strongly advised to make ship purchase decision in depressed freight market period, during which the ship price remains much cheaper than that of boom time. This investment decision is very critical to preparing the future decision to sell out the invested asset at higher price for realizing a huge capital gain. Otherwise, the shipping firms are very vulnerable to operating loss due to unexpected collapse of non-liner shipping market like the cases of 1981, 2008, and 2012.

As a result of the importance of timing decision associated with investment on bulk carrier business, the managers are required to make an intensive effort to forecast the shipping markets accurately. Without any proper prediction system for the freight markets, it is not possible for the shipping firms to improve their financial performance.

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